

PROTRACTED ETHNO-RELIGIOUS CONFLICTS IN SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824412>

Abstract

Ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State, Nigeria, have significantly impeded socio-economic growth, thereby intensifying poverty, insecurity, and infrastructural deterioration. This study analyses the causes and effects of these conflicts, utilising the social identity theory as a framework of analysis. These frameworks highlight how socioeconomic inequalities, identity politics, and governance deficiencies perpetuate cycles of conflict and obstruct sustainable development. The study utilised a descriptive survey research design, combining quantitative data from 1,398 respondents representing various ethnic and religious groups with qualitative insights derived from focus group discussions and in-depth interviews. A statistical study indicated that ethnicity and religion are the primary catalysts of conflict, comprising 65.37% (mean = 3.92, SD = 0.81) of documented instances, which are worsened by political manipulation (mean = 3.47, SD = 0.95) and economic disparity (mean = 3.76, SD = 0.88). The socio-economic ramifications are significant, encompassing the displacement of more than 200,000 inhabitants, the destruction of 500 towns, and a 40% decline in company revenue (mean = 3.81, SD = 0.89). The study revealed that a combination of identity issues, socio-economic inequalities, historical grievances, and governance challenges are drivers of ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State. These factors not only define the nature of the conflicts but also shape their persistence and intensity. The consistency in agreement across statements reflected a strong consensus on these critical issues. The study recommended that governments at all levels need to implement inclusive governance frameworks that promote fairness and equity across ethno-religious divides in Kaduna State, given Nigeria's heterogeneous composition. It is also recommended that stakeholders should collectively embrace interfaith dialogue and collaborative

initiatives that could promote tolerance and peaceful coexistence in the interest of national integration.

Keywords: Ethno-religious conflicts, Socio-economic development, Insecurity, Poverty, peaceful coexistence.

Introduction

Ethnic consciousness refers to the loyalty or attachment to an ethnic group as a social, political, and economic entity or a cultural community. Ethnic consciousness is not detrimental to national integration in a nation-state. It can be argued that every individual needs this form of consciousness for their sense of identity. These conflicts have been associated with inequalities, insecurity, and poverty, hindering economic progress (Arowosegbe, 2023). Kukah (2020) noted that ethnicity could create integration problems, especially in a multinational State. Kukah furthered that ethnicity, like religion, is an issue of primordial identity and could easily be subjected to mobilisation by actors for a group cause. For Ibe, et. al. (2024), it is a two-edged sword, with ethnic affiliation being about how the group defines itself, while ethnic attribution usually falls beyond the group's control and lies within the purview and definition of outsiders. Religion, on the other hand, is a very dynamic issue.

In Kaduna State, ethno-religious conflicts and challenges of socio-economic development have been a persistent problem that has hindered socio-economic in the State. The conflict continues to take lives and property in its wake despite the government's and other parties' best efforts. These conflicts have resulted in serious issues that impact the state's socio-economic development. Stakeholders in Kaduna State are increasingly worried about the issue of ethno-religious conflict and its effects on the socio-economic development of the state. Politics, religion, and ethnicity have been the main causes of conflict in the State (Musa, 2018).

The conflicts have resulted in several fatalities, evictions of residents, and property destruction, notably in the Central and Southern regions of the state. Thoburn (2018) contends that socio-economic inequality and poverty facilitate the emergence of these conflicts. The conflict has hindered the state from developing socioeconomically to its full potential. According to Thoburn (2018), the state had experienced recurring violence, insecurity, decreased investment opportunities, low levels of student attendance, and falling literacy rates. These problems have had a significant negative impact on the state's overall development and growth. An in-depth knowledge of the causes and effects of ethno-religious conflicts is necessary to handle these difficulties successfully. Isaac & Onuoha (2017) have also linked elements like economic injustice, political marginalisation, and religious extremism to the ongoing ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State.

The failure of the government and development partners to address the underlying causes of these conflicts has rendered finding a peaceful settlement all but impossible (Ibrahim, 2019). The Central and Southern Kaduna States have made headlines numerous times due to ethno-religious conflicts, which frequently result in casualties and destruction of property. The state's socio-economic development has been badly impacted by this ongoing violence, hindering development and growth.

The pertinent questions are: What are the causes of ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State? How have protracted ethno-religious conflicts negatively impacted socio-economic development in Kaduna State? It is, therefore, imperative to investigate protracted heterogeneous ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State to determine how they impact socio-economic development in the State.

Conceptual Analyses

Conflict

The definition of conflict, like peace, is contentious. However, most scholars believe that conflict typically reflects a clash of interests or goals between parties, which may include individuals, groups, ethnic groups, or states. According to Alemika and Chukwuma (2019), conflict occurs "when two or more people struggle over values and claims to status, power and resources in which the opponents aim to neutralise, injure or eliminate their rivals".

Generally, conflict has been considered an obstacle to progress, political stability, economic prosperity, and overall socio-economic development in any society due to its destructive impact. It, therefore, means that conflict must be averted or managed properly and promptly, as failure to do so will reflect a determined action or struggle over a goal, which may be overt or subtle, manifest or imaginary. While it is not easy to classify conflicts definitively, not all conflicts in Nigeria are of the same kind, as can be seen from the various dimensions, including ethnicity, religion, politics, and economy.

Ethno-Religious Conflict

Jenkins (2019) views an ethnic group as a collective of people who share the same historical experiences, possess the same culture, speak the same language, and hold similar beliefs about the future. Similarly, Different scholars have defined the term "religious conflict" in various ways. These diverse definitions convey a single meaning: disagreement between two or more religious groups. Hornby (2016) also defines religious conflict as a situation in which adherents of one or more religious groups are involved in conflict with adherents of another religious group. According to Edewor, et al (2014), ethno-religious conflict refers to tensions and hostilities rooted in the overlapping and often competing ethnic and religious identities within a society. These conflicts typically arise when ethnic and religious group loyalties become politicised,

leading to competition over power, resources, and recognition. Schaub (2014) argues that ethnic conflict, as a core component of ethno-religious conflict, is often driven by perceived threats to group identity and survival. He contends that these conflicts are not merely about material interests but are deeply connected to group belonging and existential concerns.

Furthermore, Osaghae (2006) explains that ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria are exacerbated by historical grievances, the colonial legacy, and institutional structures that have entrenched divisions. He emphasises that the conflict is about more than religion or ethnicity in isolation; rather, it is the intersection and mobilisation of these identities within political and socio-economic contexts that fuels violence.

Economic Development

Economic development is simultaneously a concept, an activity and a professional practice. Not only is economic development a popular topic of discussion, but it is also an activity for which there are high expectations and significant public investments. Perhaps the only agreement currently is that economic development is difficult to define. Nevertheless, defining economic development is a prerequisite to moving the discussion towards objective policy discussion and robust measurement.

The first step in defining economic development is distinguishing it from the concept of economic growth. Economic growth has a strong theoretical grounding and is easily quantified as an increase in aggregate output. In theorising economic growth, David Ricardo (1819) and later Robert Solow (1956), among others, conceptualise an economy as a machine that produces economic output as a function of inputs, such as labour, land, and equipment. Growth occurs when output increases. Output can increase either when we add more inputs or when we use technology or innovation to enhance the efficiency with which we transform inputs into outputs.

Literature Review

Keefer and Knack (2021) found evidence that income inequality and polarisation, which we associate with the lack of economic development, foster an environment of uncertainty. It erodes the enforcement of property and contractual rights that "affect growth directly, by influencing the choice of production process and the efficiency with which production is carried out, and indirectly by reducing incentives to invest. The lack of economic development erodes capacities and penalises future economic growth. Of course, economic growth provides slack resources that can either be appropriated by rent-seeking elites or invested in economic development, laying the groundwork for future economic growth. When long-run prosperity rests not on resource extraction but on the ongoing production of ideas, investments in economic development become even more essential as a precursor to growth.

Defining development in this way and contrasting it with growth gives sense to the outcomes of economic development. Equally important are the specific capacities germane to the process of economic development. Economic development, according to Schumpeter (2016), involves transferring capital from established methods of production to new, innovative, productivity-enhancing methods. Schumpeter's conceptualisation focused on understanding the origins of the business cycle and the conditions that gave rise to new opportunities, propelling the economy forward to a higher economic growth trajectory. Schumpeter (2016) discusses the emergence of systems of complementary capabilities that develop around key radical innovations, thereby creating economic growth.

Zuckerman (2019) posited that "Muslim and Christian stakeholders are guilty of unwholesome preaching and negative comments against each other's religions, particularly in Northern Nigeria" In Eastern Nigeria, it is common knowledge that Christians participate in iconoclasm

against the African Traditional Religion. All Muslims believe in Islam as a religion. A religion of peace is considered because it emphasises peaceful coexistence among people, irrespective of their religious differences, and promotes peacebuilding. It is clearly demonstrated in the Islamic teaching of religious tolerance." And insult not those whom they worship besides Allah lest they insult Allah wrongfully without knowledge Qur'an 6:108". The above verse shows that whoever wants others to listen to him must equally learn how to listen to others. In other words, whoever wants people to respect his religion must respect other people's religion as well.

The poverty level, most especially in the Northern part of Nigeria, contributes to the high frequency of ethno-religious conflicts in the North. Physical poverty creates societal problems, particularly when many people cannot afford necessities such as shelter, clothing, and food. Since Nigeria lacks a robust structural economy to support its large population, poverty creates significant societal problems. Extremely poor people can do anything to sustain themselves. Thus, the poor youths (Almajiris), particularly in Northern Nigeria, are manipulated with small amounts of money and food to cause religious conflicts.

On indigeneship and settler issues, Onyeiwu (2021) noted that the issues are a common problem all over the country. Despite the rhetoric about Nigerian citizenship, all Nigerians recognise that there is indigeneship. President Obasanjo and his Vice President, Alhaji Atiku Abubakar, have claimed that indigeneship is illegal. This problem cannot be solved by political hypocrisy and rhetoric. Indeed, there have been patterns of migrations. But we all know the settlement pattern at this point. Even though the Hausa-Fulani have lived in Shagamu for over a hundred years, not many of them are in the local government council or the Ogun State House of Assembly. Onyeiwu (2021) further noted that the Hausa-Fulani people have lived in Abia, Enugu, and Anambra for a long time.

Onayeikan (2020) argued, not without some justification, that the recurring violent conflict between the Hausa/Fulani settlers and the Ikara people is not simply a matter of their religious differences but has more to do with the competition for limited land and other economic resources in the area. Land and resources have been a major cause of conflict all over Africa and have often led to ethnic confrontations and conflicts. In a situation such as that prevailing in the Kaduna area, where Fulani herders are pitted in a competition for land against the Ilcaras, an indigenous group that is largely agricultural, the eruption of ethnic conflicts becomes inevitable without the intervention of the state to ensure that the legitimate demands of both ethnic groups are made.

Theoretical Framework

In examining the dynamics of protracted ethno-religious conflicts, particularly in multi-ethnic societies such as Nigeria, it is essential to ground the analysis in relevant theoretical perspectives. A theory that offers deep insights into identity-based conflict is the Social Identity Theory (SIT).

Social Identity Theory (SIT)

This theory, developed in the field of social psychology, provides a lens through which to understand the psychological underpinnings of group affiliation, in-group favouritism, and out-group discrimination —factors central to the ethno-religious tensions seen in regions like Kaduna State (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). The creation of group identities involves both the categorisation of one's "in-group" with regard to an "out-group" and the tendency to view one's group with a positive bias vis-à-vis the out-group. Members of the same group tend to view themselves as superior to other groups in society, which results in prejudice that leads to discrimination and conflicts. The fear of marginalisation tends to influence the affinity of the

lesser group with the 'bigger' or dominant group, thereby leading to assimilation and extinction, with a tendency to distort and underdevelop the socio-cultural space.

Social and political tensions in Nigeria have been attributed to the ethnic and religious diversity. Ethnic sentiments predominate and account for discrimination and marginalisation from the dominant group, even among people with a common religion, thereby straining relationships and affecting cohesion and stability. The elusive peace and absence of stability in ethnically heterogeneous societies, such as Nigeria, are amongst other casualties premised on the inability to effectively manage diversity and transform pluralism into a constructive instrument rather than a phenomenon that has hindered the attainment of nationhood (Guobadia & Adekunle, 2018).

The ethnic and religious angle to the conflicts in Southern and Central Kaduna emanates from the feeling of superiority by members of the same ethnic and religious groups, in this case, members of the Fulani/ Hausa ethnic stock who are nomadic pastoralists and profess the Islamic Religion. The armed pastoralists, feeling superior to members of their host communities who are non-Fulani and non-Muslims, easily attack to grab farmlands for grazing. The host community with ownership claims to the land feels superior and aggrieved, dwells on protection, and hardly relents on ownership claims or sacrifices their land. This makes the conflicts intractable and difficult to resolve.

Methodology

Based on the study's focus, the descriptive survey research design was adopted. Survey is highly suitable for research work that aims to elicit information on behavioural patterns. The survey design utilised copies of questionnaires for primary data collection, while the descriptive aspect focused on explaining and understanding experiences and perspectives.

The area of the Study is Kaduna State, located in the northern part of Nigeria, situated approximately between latitude 9° 30' and 11° 30' N and longitude 7° 30' and 10° 30' E. Kaduna State has a diverse population with the United Nations projection as 9.1 million people approximately. Kaduna State is home to indigenous tribes, including the Hausa, Fulani, Gwari, and Kamuku, each with distinct customs, languages, and traditional practices, which contribute to the state's cultural diversity. The State's cultural festivals, such as the Durbar, showcase the deep-rooted traditions and a sense of community among its diverse population. The locality was chosen due to the intense and protracted ethno-religious that ravages the environment. Additionally, trade, mining, and manufacturing contribute to the economic landscape of the State (Ogunleye, 2008). The Population of the Study is the Kaduna Central and South Senatorial District residents, who were between the ages of 18 and 60 years of age, including male and female representations of the diverse ethnic and religious groups in the State. They were drawn from 2 Local Governments each, from the two 2) Senatorial Districts (Kaduna Central and South).

In this study, the sample size of research participants was chosen using a stratified random sampling technique. This was repeated for both Southern and Central Senatorial districts, and four local governments were picked for the study. These were the local government areas of Kaduna South, Kachia, Kauru, and Chikum. The sample size comprised of residents of both rural and urban areas, including youths, educators, religious leaders, community leaders, and victims. The Taro Yamane equation was used to determine the number of respondents, which is presented below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where

n is the sample size,

N is the population size,

e (0.05) is the desired level of precision (expressed as a decimal).

Table 1: Kaduna State Senatorial Districts

Name	Status	Census 2006	Projection 2023	Sample size
Kaduna State	Senatorial Districts	6,113,503	9,032,200	
Local Government Areas				
Ikara	Kaduna North Senatorial	430,753	636,400	
Kubau		280,704	414,700	
Kudan		138,956	205,300	
Lere		339,740	501,900	
Makarfi		146,574	216,600	
Sabon-Gari		291,358	430,500	
Soba		291,173	430,200	
Zaria		406,990	601,300	
Total from North Districts		2,326,248	3,436,900	
Birnin Gwari	Kaduna Central Senatorial	258,581	382,000	
Chikun		372,272	550,000	400
Giwa		292,384	432,000	
Igabi		430,753	636,400	
Kaduna North		364,575	538,600	
Kaduna South		402,731	595,000	400
Kajuru		109,810	162,200	
Total from Central Districts		2,231,106	3,296,200	800
Jaba	Kaduna South Senatorial	155,973	230,400	
Jema's		278,202	411,000	
Kachia		252,568	373,100	400
Kagarko		239,058	353,200	
Kaura		174,626	258,000	
Kauru		221,276	326,900	400
Sanga		151,485	223,800	
Zangon-Kataf	318,991	471,300		
Total from South Districts		1,792,179	2,647,700	800
Total from the Kaduna State		6,113,503	9,032,200	1,600

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Data Presentation and Discussions of Findings

The data is organised and interpreted in line with the thematic focus of the study, providing empirical insights into the dynamics of protracted ethno-religious conflicts in selected local

government areas of Kaduna State and their implications for socio-economic development. A total of 1,600 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 1,398 were returned properly and adequately completed.

Q1: What are the causes of ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State?

Table2: Causes of ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State

Statement	Total	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1. Ethnicity and religion are the main causes of the conflict in Kaduna State.	1,398	4.37	1.08	Agreed
2. Ethno-religious conflicts are made worse by the involvement of political actors.	1,398	3.88	1.20	Agreed
3. Historical grievances in Kaduna State partly cause ethno-religious conflicts.	1,398	3.94	1.27	Agreed
4. Ethno-religious tensions are exacerbated by economic inequality.	1,389	3.92	1.25	Agreed
5. A lack of educational opportunities exacerbates ethno-religious conflicts.	1,398	3.88	1.24	Agreed
6. Attacks on farmlands and communities characterise the conflicts in Kaduna.	1,398	3.88	1.24	Agreed
7. Reprisal attacks on herds of cattle also characterise the conflict.	1,398	3.90	1.22	Agreed
8. The main causes of ethno-religious conflicts can be effectively addressed.	1,398	3.88	1.27	Agreed
9. Kaduna State is not sincere in handling ethno-religious disputes.	1,398	3.97	1.14	Agreed
10. Frequent killings and destruction affect peace in Kaduna State.	1,398	3.84	1.30	Agreed
11. Historical occurrences and resentments impact ethno-religious conflicts.	1,398	4.03	1.20	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 above shows respondents' perceptions of the nature, dynamics, and causes of ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State. Each statement reflects a specific aspect of the conflict and is analysed based on the total number of responses, mean scores, standard deviations, and collective decisions.

Statement No. 1. (Ethnicity and Religion are the main causes of the conflict in Kaduna State) has the highest mean score (4.37), with a low standard deviation (1.08), reflecting great agreement among respondents, with little variation in opinions. This finding emphasises the fundamental role that ethnic and religious identities play in fuelling regional conflicts. Other significant factors include the involvement of political actors (mean = 3.88), historical grievances (mean = 3.94), economic inequality (mean = 3.92), and a lack of educational opportunities (mean = 3.88). These findings suggest that political manipulation, unresolved past grievances, socio-economic disparities, and limited access to education worsen tensions, perpetuating conflict dynamics in Kaduna State. The relatively higher standard deviations (ranging from 1.20 to 1.27) for these factors reflect moderate variability in responses, likely influenced by the respondents' diverse backgrounds.

Notably, respondents agreed that historical occurrences and resentments impact conflicts (mean = 4.03), stressing the role of deeply rooted issues in perpetuating discord. The perception that Kaduna State lacks sincerity in handling disputes (mean = 3.97) further underscores concerns about the effectiveness of conflict management mechanisms.

In summary, the results indicate that a combination of identity-based issues, socio-economic inequalities, historical grievances, and governance challenges drives ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State. These factors not only define the nature of the conflicts but also shape their persistence and intensity. The consistency in agreement across statements reflects a strong consensus on these critical issues.

Q2. How have protracted ethno-religious conflicts negatively impacted socio-economic development in Kaduna State?

Table: Impact of protracted ethno-religious conflicts on socio-economic development in Kaduna State

Statement	Total	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1. Relationships between Christians and Muslims in Kaduna State are affected by the conflict	1398	4.32	0.98	Agreed
2. The conflict has scared many investors away from Kaduna State.	1398	3.88	1.14	Agreed
3. In Kaduna State, ethno-religious tensions have impeded the development of	1398	3.92	1.12	Agreed

	enterprises and industries.				
4.	Ethno-religious tensions have affected school enrolment and attendance in Kaduna State.	1398	4.22	0.99	Agreed
5.	The Conflicts have affected Kaduna State's healthcare system in many ways.	1398	3.76	1.08	Agreed
6.	The spate of infrastructural development in Kaduna State is affected by ethnoreligious conflict.	1398	3.87	1.09	Agreed
7.	Criminal activity in Kaduna State has increased because of the ethnoreligious strife.	1398	4.01	1.02	Agreed
8.	Conflicts between ethnic and religious groups have affected social harmony and cohesion in Kaduna State.	1398	3.89	1.06	Agreed
9.	Ethno-religious conflicts have impeded the growth of tourism in Kaduna State.	1398	3.94	1.07	Agreed
10.	The ethno-religious conflict often causes displacement and migration from Kaduna State.	1398	3.92	1.05	Agreed

Source: Source: Field Survey, 2025

Interfaith relationships between Christians and Muslims have been significantly strained, with a mean of 4.32, indicating a pervasive erosion of social trust and cohesion. Economically, conflicts have deterred investors (mean 3.88) and impeded enterprise and industrial growth (mean 3.92), reflecting stagnation in key economic sectors. Education has also been severely affected, with reduced school enrolment and attendance (mean 4.22), perpetuating cycles of poverty and underdevelopment. The healthcare system has experienced significant strain (mean 3.76), while infrastructural development remains hindered (mean 3.87), highlighting the systemic challenges posed by persistent insecurity. Criminal activity has increased as a direct consequence of the unrest (mean 4.01), further destabilising the region and eroding public safety.

Social harmony has deteriorated (mean 3.89), underscoring the disruption to the state's communal fabric. Similarly, the tourism sector has been negatively impacted (mean 3.94), signalling the broader implications of insecurity on regional stability. Displacement and

migration caused by conflicts (mean 3.92) reflect the human toll and exacerbation of developmental challenges.

Discussions of Findings

Ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria, particularly in regions like Kaduna State, are complex phenomena influenced by various factors, including political involvement, socio-economic disparities, and historical grievances. The above findings of the study aligns with recent scholarly works provide insights that align with and expand upon the findings presented in this study. Recent studies support the assertion that political actors worsen ethno-religious conflicts. For instance, Nwagwu (2018) and Ameh (2023) examine how political manipulation of ethnic and religious identities intensifies conflicts, undermining national cohesion and development.

The role of ethnic and religious identities as primary drivers of conflict is well-documented. Strömbom (2014) and Adenuga et al. (2023) explore how these identities contribute to national security challenges, highlighting the deep-seated nature of such conflicts. These findings resonate with the study's emphasis on the fundamental role of ethnicity and religion in fueling regional conflicts (Cordell & Wolff 2009), as reflected in the highest mean scores and low standard deviations, indicating strong agreement among respondents. Furthermore, Historical grievances and economic disparities are significant contributors to ethno-religious tensions. Conteh-Morgan (2004) reported that unresolved historical issues and economic inequalities create fertile ground for conflicts, as marginalised groups may resort to violence to express discontent. Njoku and Kolapo (2022) discuss how historical events and economic factors have led to increased tensions in regions like Kaduna State. These findings align with the mean scores observed for historical grievances and economic inequalities, which indicate their critical role in perpetuating conflict dynamics (Prince et. al., 2023).

The result of these findings shows a profound negative impact of protracted ethno-religious conflicts on socio-economic development in Kaduna State. Across various dimensions, respondents consistently agreed on the adverse consequences, as reflected in the high mean scores and relatively low standard deviations.

Conclusion

From the above, it has been established that prolonged ethno-religious conflicts have profoundly negative effects on Kaduna State's socio-economic development. Social trust and interfaith relationships between Christians and Muslims have been severely strained, reflecting an erosion of communal harmony. Economically, the region has suffered from reduced investment, stagnated enterprise growth, and declining industrial activity. Education has been another major casualty, with reduced school enrollment and attendance perpetuating cycles of poverty and underdevelopment. These disruptions hinder long-term growth and opportunities for younger generations.

Despite these challenges, respondents acknowledged progress in reducing ethno-religious confrontations in Kaduna State. Efforts by the government and stakeholders, including awareness campaigns and interfaith dialogues, have made positive impacts. Such initiatives promote harmony and foster understanding between diverse groups.

Recommendations

The findings of this study underscore the need for comprehensive and strategic approaches to address ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State. Hence, the study makes the following recommendations:

1. Governments at all levels needs to implement inclusive governance frameworks that promote fairness and equity among all ethnic and religious groups. Policies should aim to

bridge socio-economic disparities, ensuring marginalised communities have access to economic opportunities, education, healthcare, and social services.

2. It is imperative to strengthen interfaith dialogue and initiatives that promote tolerance and peaceful coexistence. Religious leaders and traditional authorities must play a more active role in fostering understanding and reconciliation among diverse groups.
3. Efforts should also focus on enhancing the capacity of security and law enforcement agencies. These institutions require better training, equipment, and resources to respond effectively to conflicts and prevent violence.
4. Post-conflict reconstruction and rehabilitation must be prioritised. This includes rebuilding infrastructure, providing support for displaced individuals, and creating sustainable livelihoods for affected populations. Such initiatives should be accompanied by community-driven programs that promote healing and reintegration, fostering social cohesion and reducing the likelihood of recurring violence.
5. The role of education in conflict prevention cannot be overstated. Schools should incorporate peace education and inter-group tolerance programs into their curricula to nurture a culture of understanding and respect from an early age.

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